

**Society for the Study of Psychology and Wesleyan Thought
Wesleyan Philosophical Society**

**Annual Meeting, March 4, 2010
Azusa Pacific University**

Gift and Economy: Ethics, Hospitality, and the Market

Society for the Study of Psychology and Wesleyan Thought

Meeting at a Glance

7:00-8:00 Registration

8:00 Welcome

8:15-9:00 Morning Plenary Address

9:00-9:45 Panel Response and Questions

10:00 – 12:00 Morning Parallel Group Sessions

12:15 – 1:15 Lunch / SSPWT Annual Meeting

1:30 – 2:30 Plenary Session with Response from Dr. Robert Hamerton-Kelly

2:45 – 4:45 Afternoon Parallel Group Sessions

6:30 Banquet

**8:15-9:00 Morning Plenary Address: Dr. Robert
Hamerton-Kelly**

- Respondent: Dean Blevins

9:00-9:45 Panel Response and Questions

10:00 – 12:00 Morning Parallel Group Sessions

Session A: Psychology, Pastoral Ministry, and Cross-cultural Service

- Dick Pritchard, D.Min. (Azusa Pacific University) – “Early Assessment and Training of Undergraduate Ministry Interns”

- Chris Adams, Ph.D. (Azusa Pacific University) – “The Duke Clergy Health Initiative: A Theoretical Model of the Holistic Health of United Methodist Clergy”
- Alice Fok, M.A. (Azusa Pacific University) – “A Systems Perspective on Cultural Adjustment in Long-Term Overseas Missionaries”
- William Whited & Ronald W. Wright, Ph.D. (Mount Vernon Nazarene University) – “Initiating and Sustaining Motivations for Serving the Poor in Romania: A Qualitative Analysis”

Session B: Psychology, Peacemaking & Ethics

- Al Dueck, Ph.D. (Fuller Graduate School of Psychology) – “A Peaceable Psychology”
- Robert Duke, Ph.D. (Azusa Pacific University) – “Peacemaking Left Behind: Can Orthopathy Help Evangelicals Promote Peace?”
- David Goodman, Ph.D. (Harvard University) – “Awakening to the Other: Trauma, Violence, and Ethics in Levinas”

Session C: Neuropsychology & Ethics

- Warren Brown, Ph.D. (Fuller Graduate School of Psychology), Gregory Peterson, Ph.D. (South Dakota State University), Kevin Reimer, Ph.D. (Azusa Pacific University), Michael L. Spezio, Ph.D. (Scripps College & California Institute of Technology), & James A. Van Slyke, M.A., M.S. (Fuller Graduate School of Psychology) – “Virtue Ethics and Decision Neuroscience: Theory and Research”
- Sam Powell, Ph.D. (Point Loma Nazarene University) – “Christian Ethics and Altruism: A Proposal”
- Doug Milne, M.Div. (Northeastern Seminary) – “Wesley and Psychology: A Glimpse into the Wesleyan Mind”

Session D: Psychology, Moral Theory & Hospitality

- Giancarlo Tarantino (Loyola University Chicago) & Ronald Wright, Ph.D. (Mount Vernon Nazarene University) – “The Temporality of Gift Giving Within a Modern Capitalist Economy: Jean Vanier and Soren Kierkegaard in Dialogue With Erich Fromm and Karl Marx”
- Mark Maddix, Ph.D. (Northwest Nazarene University) – “Unite the pair so long disjoined: Justice and Empathy in Moral Development Theory”

- Arvin Gouw, M.A. (Johns Hopkins University School of Medicine) – “Psychological and moral maturity is necessary for Christians in practicing good ethics and hospitality”
- Beverly Hall, D.Min. (Chapel Hill United Methodist Church) – “Pineapple Hospitality in A Fruitcake World: A Wesleyan Perspective on Radical Hospitality”

12:15 – 1:15 Lunch / SSPWT Annual Meeting

1:30 – 2:30 Afternoon Plenary Session with Response from Dr. Robert Hamerton-Kelly

Warren Brown, Ph.D. (Fuller Graduate School of Psychology), Scott Garrels, Ph.D. (Fuller Graduate School of Psychology), & Kevin Reimer, Ph.D. (Azusa Pacific University) – “Redeeming Imitation: Fostering Mimetic Compassions in Communities”

2:45 – 4:45 Afternoon Parallel Group Sessions:

Session A: *Psychology, Christian Worship, and Ecclesiology*

- Nell Becker Sweeden (Boston University) & Brent Peterson, Ph.D. (Northwest Nazarene University) – “Scripture, Sacrament, and Ethics: How the Word and Table Shapes the Economic and Political Life of the Church as Gift in a Spirit of Hospitality”
- Alexis Abernethy, Ph.D. (Fuller Graduate School of Psychology) – “Worship, Models, and Relationships: Integrating the Work of Rene Girard”
- Anna Hawley & Ronald Wright, Ph.D. (Mount Vernon Nazarene University) – “Attachment Patterns, Theological Defensiveness, and Interpersonal Generosity: An Exploration of Related Constructs”

Session B: *Psychotherapy & Ethics*

- Marv Erisman, Ph.D. (Azusa Pacific University) – “Interactional Consciousness”
- Scott Grover, M.A. (Fuller Graduate School of Psychology) – “The Violence of the Market Economy and Psychotherapy as a Gift”
- Lisa Finlay, M.A. (Fuller Graduate School of Psychology) – “Disruption, Fear, and Chaos: Exploring the Exceptional Desire”

Session C: *Psychology, Mimetic Virtue & Christian Ethics*

- Michael Leffel, Ph.D. (Point Loma Nazarene University) - “Putting on Virtue: Social Grace and Mimetic Virtue – A New Direction for Practical Christian Ethics”
- Ross Oakes-Mueller, Ph.D., Juliana Karras, Dane Cardiel, Nickolas Gebhart, Carrie Sparks, John Games, Thane Erikson, Ph.D., & Brittany Shook (Point Loma Nazarene University) - “Putting on Virtue”: Mimetic Virtue and the Michelangelo Phenomenon – A New Direction for Theory, Research, and Practice”

Session D: *Parenting and Family Therapy*

- Beth Houskamp, Ph.D., Paul Shrier, Ph.D., Cathleen Shrier, Ph.D., & Stephanie Miyake (Azusa Pacific University) – “A Theological and Neurodevelopmental Model for Christian Parenting”
- Daniel Sweeney, Ph.D. (George Fox University) – “Play Therapy: The Experience of Grace for Hurting Children”
- Carrie Horn, M.A. (Azusa Pacific University) – “Perfectionism: An Antagonist of Grace”

Wesleyan Philosophical Society

Meeting at a Glance

- 7:00-8:00 Registration
- 8:00 Welcome
- 8:15-9:00 Morning Plenary Address: Dr. Robert Hammerton-Kelly
- 9:00-9:45 Panel Response and Questions
- 9:45-10:00 Break
- 10:00-11:45 Session 1
- 11:45-12:45 Lunch/Business Meeting
- 1:00- 2:30 Session 2
- 2:30-2:45 Break
- 2:45-4:15 Session 3
- 4:15-4:30 Break
- 4:30-5:45 Session 4
- 6:45-7:30 Banquet Dinner and Plenary Address

9:45-10:00 Break

10:00-11:45 Session 1

Session 1A

- Young Ko, Violence, War, and Economy in Girard's Theory of Mimetic Desire
- Jonathan Heaps, Shopping Alone: Girard's Triangular Desire and How Advertising Isolates
- Geoffrey Holsclaw, Christ in Circulation: The Eucharistic Exchange and Money

Session 1B

- Karl Aho, *For Others or for Profit? A Greek/Jew/Jewish Alternative to Market-mediated Relationships*
- Benjamin Suriano, *Gift and Grace beyond the Market Ontology: Constituting the Subject Otherwise.*
- Marion Grau, *'Unjust Stewards,' Financial Markets and Gift Economies: Supercapitalism's Confidence Men, and the Structures of Unaccountability*

Session 1C

- Lara Helfe, *The Role of Faith in Giving*
- Eric Manchester, *Modernity, Personhood, and the Displacement of the Divine With the Economy*
- Kent Dunnington, *Punishment, Exchange, and Gift*

11:45-12:45 Lunch/Business Meeting

1:00- 2:30 Session 2

Session 2A

- Anselm Min, *What is Economy? Some Foundational Reflections on Its Apriori Conditions and the Possibility of Its Humanization*
- Tim Crutcher, *Gift and Economy, Grace and Limitation: A Clarification of Concepts*

Session 2B

- Craig Hovey, *History as Sacrament: The Joy of Living Non-instrumentalized Time*
- Craig Keen, *Prelude to the Resurrection of the Flesh: Speaking of Bodies*

2:30-2:45 Break

2:45-4:15 Session 3

Session 3A

- Thomas Bridges, *'Survival of the Hegelianest': A Bergsonian Dismantling of Deterministic Economics Inherited from Hegel*
- Nathan Crawford, *Christianity as Post-Capitalist Apparatus: Appropriating Agamben's Thinking for a Critique of Capitalism*
- John Wright, *Process Philosophy as the Onto-theo-logic of State-Regulated Capitalism: The Economics of Nihilism*

Session 3B

- Joshua Kira, *Love and Commands: The Fall as a Metaethical Schism*
- Teri Merrick, Beholding a mathematically beautiful cosmos as gift?
- Steven Huizenga, *Responsibility and Option Luck*

Session 3C

- John Brittingham, *Pharmakonomics or The Gift That Keeps on Giving?*
- Sharon Harvey, *Presenting of the Gift and the Economy of Exchange*
- Randy Ramal, *Recovering the Gift for Economies of Exchange*

4:15-4:30 Break

4:30-5:45 Session 4

Session 4A

- John McAtee, The Gifts of God for the People of God: The Gift as Communion in Babette's Feast
- Michael Rodgers, *Remembering Camus: Towards A Relative Philosophy of Liberation*
- Joseph Bankard, *Is Christian Hope a Form of Long Term Economy: An argument from the writings of Albert Camus?*

Session 4B

- Paul Bofo, *A Reflection on the Socio-Economic Ethics of John Wesley and the Poverty of Third World Economies*
- Josh Sweeden, *Theology of Work: A Conversation in Economy, Ethics, and Community Practice*
- Bryan Williams, *John Wesley's Successful Gift: A Prolegomenon to a Wesleyan Philosophy of Health Care*

6:30 P.M.-7:30 P.M. Banquet Dinner and Plenary Address **Dr. Robert Hammerton-Kelly**

**Wesleyan Theological Society
Annual Meeting
March 5-6, 2010**

Meeting at a Glance

Friday March 5

	Registration
7:45-8:20	Welcome
8:30-9:50	Parallel Session #1
10:00-11:20	Plenary Session
11:30-12:50	Parallel Session #2
1:00-2:20	Lunch and Meeting of the Executive Committee
2:30-3:50	Parallel Session #3
4:00-5:20	Plenary Session
5:30-6:30	Annual Business Meeting
7:00	Banquet and Presidential Address

Saturday March 6

7:30-7:50	Morning Prayers
8:00-9:20	Parallel Session #4
9:20-10:20	Poster Presentations and Women Students' Reception
10:30-11:50	Parallel Session #5
12:00-12:50	Closing Worship
1:00-2:30	Lunch and Meeting of Program Chairs

FRIDAY MARCH 5

7:45-8:20. Welcome

8:30-9:50. Parallel Session #1

Scripture _____

Panel: Joel B. Green, *Body, Soul, and Human Life: The Nature of Humanity in the Bible* (Baker, 2008).

Moderator: Thomas E. Phillips, Point Loma Nazarene University

Panelists:

Joel B. Green, Fuller Theological Seminary
Andy Johnson, Nazarene Theological Seminary
Sarah Marion, Fuller Theological Seminary
Samuel M. Powell, Point Loma Nazarene University
Frank Anthony Spina, Seattle Pacific University

Historical Studies

Theme: “The Future of Scripture at the End of the Age: Perfection, the End of Time, and Scriptural Interpretation in the American Holiness Movement of the Nineteenth Century”

- Moderator: Bernie A. Van De Walle, Ambrose University College
- Steven Hoskins, Trevecca Nazarene University, “*The 11th Hour of the Day in Music City, USA: The Pentecostal Mission, the Bible, and the end of Time.*”
- Thomas A. Miles, Southern Methodist University, “*The Use of Scripture in Interpreting the Doctrine of Christian Perfection in the Nineteenth Century Holiness Movement.*”
- Andrew J. Wood, Auburn University, “*Unmethodistic Methodism: Authority(ies) and Scriptural Holiness in Connectional Context.*”

Systematic Theology

- Moderator: K. Steve McCormick, Nazarene Theological Seminary
- J. Robert Douglass, Ashland Theological Seminary, “*Break Thou the Bread of Life: The Sacrament of the Word.*”
- Douglas M. Koskela, Seattle Pacific University, “*Revelation and Formation: Sketches of a Pneumatology of Holy Scripture.*”
- Nathan Kerr (Trevecca Nazarene University) and Craig Keen (Azusa Pacific University), “*On Teaching the Dead to Praise God.*”

Philosophical Theology

Theme: “Paul and 20th Century Philosophy”

- Moderator: Heather Ross, Pt. Loma Nazarene University
- Timothy Sommer, Chicago Theological Seminary, “*Paul (as a Deconstructionist).*”
- Thomas Bridges, Marquette University, “*Pauline Paramnesia and Badiou’s Betrayal of the Event.*”

- Nathan Crawford, Indiana Wesleyan University, *“The Revolutionary Paul: An Engagement with the Philosophical Appropriation of Paul by Badiou, Žižek, and Agamben.”*

Practical Theology

Theme: “Text and Teaching: The role of the textual discernment in Formation and Instruction”

- Moderator: Dean G. Blevins, Nazarene Theological Seminary
- Catherine Stonehouse, Asbury Theological Seminary, *“The Faith of a Child and the Formative Power of Scripture.”*
- Mark A. Maddix and Richard P. Thompson, Northwest Nazarene University, *“Scripture as Formation: The Role of Scripture in Christian Discipleship.”*
- Paul Kwabena Boafo, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (Ghana), *“The Bible in the Formation of Hearts and Minds: A Study of Wesleyan Methodist Missionary Enterprise in Ghana.”*

Moral Theology

- Moderator: Joseph Bankard, Northwest Nazarene University
- Timothy R. Gaines, Garrett-Evangelical Theological Seminary, *“Christian Scripture and the Naming of All Things: Moral Theology in the Narratives of Naming.”*
- Jeff Stark, Senior Pastor, Erin Church of the Nazarene, *“Moral Encounter: Textual Appropriation for the Holiness Church.”*
- Andrew Carl Thompson, The Divinity School of Duke University, *“The Quadrilateral, Moral Psychology, and Theological Reflection in the Wesleyan Tradition.”*

Science and Theology

- Moderator: Mark Mann, Point Loma Nazarene University
- Eric M Vail, Marquette University, *“Navigating Beyond the Debate Between a Traditional Formulation of Creation out of Nothing and Creation out of Something.”*
- John Culp, Azusa Pacific University, *“Laws of Nature and the Intelligibility of Scripture: A Proposal for Science and Theology.”*
- Karen Winslow, Azusa Pacific University, *“Original Choice, Not Original Sin: The Scriptures’ View of Human Uniqueness.”*

10:00-11:20. Plenary session

- William J. Abraham with a response by Richard B. Hays.
- Moderator: Rob Wall

11:30-12:50. Parallel Session #2

Scripture (A)

Theme: "The Authority of Scripture"

- Moderator: William H. Malas Jr., Eastern Nazarene College
- Karen Winslow, Azusa Pacific University, "*Reading Scripture in the Future*"
- Richard P. Thompson, Northwest Nazarene University, "*Misplaced Authority: Rethinking the Role of the Bible as Scripture*"
- Samuel M. Powell, Point Loma Nazarene University, "*A Proposal for Understanding the Bible's Authority*"

Scripture (B)

Theme: "The Bible, Wesley, and Wesleyanism"

- Moderator: David Allen Ackerman, Pastor, First Church of the Nazarene in Sheridan, WY
- Peter Thomas Henderson Hatton, Wesley College, "*Samuel Wesley's Job.*"
- Ryan L. Hansen, Garrett-Evangelical Theological Seminary, "*Reading Within the Economy of Sanctification: Revisiting Wesleyan Hermeneutics.*"
- Richard W. H. Newton, Claremont Graduate University, "*Excavating the Significance of Nazareth Via the Church of the Nazarene.*"

Women's Studies

- Moderator: Susie Stanley, Messiah College
- Patti Dikes, Point Loma University, "*Finding Her Voice in Theology: A Reflection on the Female Theologians in the Church of the Nazarene from Olive Winchester to Mildred Bangs-Wynkoop to Diane Leclerc.*"
- Teri Merrick, Azusa Pacific University, "*Can Augustine Welcome Intersexed Bodies into Heaven?*"
- Carole D Spencer, George Fox University, "*Hannah Whitall Smith's 'Highway of Holiness'.*"

Systematic theology

- Moderator:
- Thomas McCall, Trinity Evangelical Divinity School, "*Wesleyan Theology and the Authority of Scripture: Historic Affirmations and Some Contemporary Concerns.*"

- David Bernard McEwan, Nazarene Theological College (Brisbane, Australia), *“The Interrelationship Between the Living and the Written Voice of God: Wesley’s Approach to the Reading, Understanding and Application of Scripture.”*
- Benjamin Elliott, Indonesia, *“Exactly the Kind of Book God Wants Us to Have: Overcoming Difficulties with the Evangelical Doctrine of Inspiration in the Autographs.”*

Practical Theology

Theme: “Shaped by the Word: Liturgical Interpretations/Expressions of Scripture”

- Moderator: James R. Cissell, Pastor, Murdo/Draper parish
- Ron Anderson, Garrett-Evangelical Theological Seminary, *“Practicing Scripture, Unsealing the Book.”*
- Robert Muthiah, Azusa Pacific University, *“Dwelling in the Word: Spirit, Text and Communal Formation.”*

Ecumenical Studies

Panel: “Leadership in Christian Higher Education”

- Moderator: Donald Thorsen, Azusa Pacific University

Panelists:

Gayle Beebe, President, Westmont College

Jerry Campbell, President, Claremont School of Theology

Richard Mouw, President, Fuller Theological Seminary

Jon Wallace, President, Azusa Pacific University

Moral Theology/Science and Theology

Topic: *An Open Conversation with John B. Cobb, Jr.*

- Moderator: Thomas Jay Oord, Northwest Nazarene University
- John B. Cobb, Jr., Claremont School of Theology, will spend the entire session answering questions from the audience pertaining to science, moral theology, and a variety of other theological topics.

Interdisciplinary Studies

- Moderator: Laurie Braaten, Judson University
- Dennis Royce, Azusa Pacific University, *“Troping the Truth: Revealing the Nature and Spiritual Meaning of Text through Improvisation.”*
- Francisca F. Ireland-Verwoerd, Church of the Nazarene (Quincy, MA), *“The Tabernacle as Installation Art: Conversations between Theology and Art.”*

- Paul Shrier, Azusa Pacific University, *"Mr. Wesley, What do you have to say about our economy now?"*

Historical Studies

- Moderator: Jason Vickers, United Theological Seminary
- Carl M. Leth, Olivet Nazarene University: *"Prophezei – A Reformation Model for Interpretation of Scripture."*
- Mark T. Mealey, Rocky Mountain College, Calgary, AB, Canada, *Wesley's Theological Realism as a Problem for a Distinctively Wesleyan Doctrine of Scripture.*
- John W. Wright, Point Loma Nazarene University: *"Irenaeus, the 'Rule of Truth,' and the Materiality of Early Christian Codices: The Historical Formation of the Logos of the Christian Book."*

1:00-2:20 Lunch and Meeting of the Executive Committee

2:30-3:50 Parallel Session #3

Scripture (A)

Theme: "The Future of Historical Criticism"

- Moderator: Brad E. Kelle, Point Loma Nazarene University
- Jeffrey Stackert, The University of Chicago, *"The Past Is the Present and the Future: Why Historical Criticism Should be the Basis for All Biblical Interpretation"*
- C. Jeanne Serrão, Mount Vernon Nazarene University, *"The Past Matters in Future Presents"*
- Kenneth Schenck, Wesley Seminary at Indiana Wesleyan University, *"A Bridge Over Lessing's Ditch: Locating Theological Interpretation within a Salvation-Historical Narrative"*

Scripture (B)

Theme: "Ancient Views of Scripture"

- Moderator: Anthony J. Tomasino, Bethel College
- William Yarchin, Azusa Pacific University, *"Scripture as a Spiritual Phenomenon: Evidence from the 11Q Psalm Scroll Colophon."*
- Bo H. Lim, Seattle Pacific University, *"Isaiah's Theology of the Word."*
- Dwight D. Swanson, Nazarene Theological College, *"The Bible and Qumran: The Nature of the Authority of Scripture."*

Historical Studies

- Moderator: Scott Kisker, Wesley Theological Seminary

- Bernie A. Van De Walle, Ambrose University College, “*Having the Mind of Christ: Is the Jesus Christ of A. B. Simpson’s Fourfold Gospel the Jesus Christ of a Fourth-Century Heretic?*”
- Harold E. Raser, Nazarene Theological Seminary, “*An Humble Bible Christian? The Ambiguous Hermeneutical Legacy of Phoebe Palmer for the Wesleyan Holiness Tradition.*”
- Jonathan Dodrill, Garrett-Evangelical Theological Seminary, “*From Second Blessing to Second Coming: The Evolution of Dispensationalism within the Holiness Hermeneutic.*”

Philosophical theology

Theme: “Philosophy and Scripture”

- Moderator:
- Douglas Yoder, Azusa Pacific University, “*The Future of Scripture in Philosophical Theology.*”
- Kyle Roberts, Bethel Seminary, “*God’s Edifying Discourse: Kierkegaard on Scripture and Subjectivity.*”
- Geoffrey Holsclaw, Marquette University, “*Scripture after Hermeneutics and Historicism: On Canonical, Sacramental, and Ecclesial Practices.*”

Systematic Theology

Panel: *The Future of Wesleyan Theology: Essays in Honor of Laurence Wood*

Moderator: Nathan Crawford

Panelists:

Laurence Wood, Asbury Theological Seminary
 Michael Pasquarello III, Asbury Theological Seminary
 Bradford McCall, Regent University
 Aaron Perry, Pastor, Wesleyan Church

Ethnic Studies

- Moderator: Daniel Castelo, Seattle Pacific University
- Rodney A. Thomas Jr., Brite Divinity School, “*Empire Studies and Ezekiel.*”
- Heather Ann Clements and Cassandra Shea, Azusa Pacific University, “*Shifts in First Peoples and Wesley’s Understanding of the Biblical Concept of Perfection.*”
- Brandon Winstead, Garrett-Evangelical Theological Seminary, “*‘We Are Responsible to God’: The Scriptural Foundations of Black Female Empowerment on the Church of the Nazarene’s Gulf Central District.*”

Moral Theology

- Moderator: Andrew Schwartz, Northwest Nazarene
- Nathan John Willowby, Marquette University, *“The Role of Scripture in Barth’s Relation Between Theology and Ethics.”*
- Rustin E. Brian, Garrett-Evangelical Theological Seminary, *“The Non-Intelligibility of Scripture in the Secular Age: An Argument for the Ethics of Christian Witness.”*
- Holland Prior, Azusa Pacific University, Haggard Graduate School of Theology, *“A Distorted Image: Women and Children Trapped in Sexual Servitude.”*

Preaching

- Moderator: Jay Akkerman, Northwest Nazarene University
- Andrew Cheatle, Hope University (Liverpool, UK), *“W.E. Sangster: Prince of Preachers & Herald of Holiness”*
- Robert F. Lay, Taylor University, *“The Use of Scripture—Scope, Sequence, and Contextualization in William Taylor’s California Sermons, 1849-1856.”*
- Bill McAlpine, Ambrose University College (Calgary AB), *“From Sacred Desk to Plexiglass: The Impact of the Built Environment in the Preaching Event.”*
- Montague Williams, Boston University School of Theology, *“The Use of Scripture in the Sermons of Martin Luther King, Jr.”*

4:00-5:20 Plenary session

- Richard B. Hays with a response by William J. Abraham
- Moderator: Rob Wall

5:30-6:30 Annual Business Meeting

7:00 Banquet and Presidential Address

SATURDAY MARCH 6

7:30-7:50 Morning Prayers, led by Elaine Heath

8:00-9:20 Parallel Session #4

Scripture (A)

Theme: “Interpreting the Old Testament”

- Moderator: Marty Alan Michelson, Southern Nazarene University

- Timothy D. Finlay, Azusa Pacific University, *“The Future of the Inductive Method of Bible Study.”*
- Alex Varughese, Mount Vernon Nazarene University, *“Hebrew Scriptures as Christian Scriptures, Some Remarks on the Wesleyan Tradition’s Responsibility to the Precious Gift of Judaism to the Church.”*
- David P. Melvin, Baylor University, *“Why Does the Way of the Wicked Prosper?’, Human and Divine Suffering in Jer. 11:18—12:13 and the Problem of Evil.”*

Scripture (B)

Theme: “Interpreting the New Testament I”

- Moderator: Keith H. Reeves, Azusa Pacific University
- Dean Flemming, European Nazarene College, *“Toward a Missional Reading of Scripture”*
- George Lyons, Northwest Nazarene University, *“Scripture in the Letters of Paul”*
- Thomas E. Phillips, Point Loma Nazarene University, *“A Doctrine of Scripture or the Interpretation of Scripture: What’s the Real Issue for Wesleyans?”*

Historical Studies

- Moderator: Thomas Buchan, Asbury Theological Seminary
- Jonathan Morgan, Marquette University, *“Beyond the Incarnation: Cyril of Alexandria’s Integrative Soteriology.”*
- Jackson Lashier, Marquette University, *“Irenaeus and the One God: A Reconsideration of his Unified Vision of Scripture.”*
- Mark Glen Bilby, Point Loma Nazarene University, *“The Exemplary Thief: Luke’s Penitent Thief as Moral Example.”*

Philosophical Theology

“The ‘Canonical Theism’ Project: A (Lively) Conversation with Billy Abraham”

Moderator: Kent Dunnington, Greenville College

Panelists:

- William Abraham, Perkins School of Theology (SMU)
- Elaine Heath, Perkins School of Theology (SMU)
- Randy Maddox, The Divinity School at Duke University
- Jason Vickers, United Theological Seminary
- Robert Wall, Seattle Pacific University

Women’s Studies

- Moderator: Karen Winslow, Azusa Pacific University
- Kathryn J Smith, Azusa Pacific University, *“There’s Something About Mary.”*
- Daryl R. Ireland, Boston University, *“The Creative Power of Scripture in the Lives of Nazarene Women in China.”*
- Abraham Antonio Ruelas, Patten University, *“Holy Book, Holy Life: Scripture and Sanctification in the Life and Ministry of Lela McConnell.”*

Preaching

- Moderator: James Paton, Foothills Alliance Church (Calgary AB)
- Charles W. Christian, Pastor, North Seattle Church of the Nazarene (Seattle WA),
- *“Shaking of the Foundation (alism): Biblical Preaching in Post-Modern Culture.”*
- Stephen Green, Southern Nazarene University, *“Preaching the Gospel & the Texts of Terror.”*
- Michael Pasquarello, Asbury Theological Seminary, *“John Wesley: Homiletic Theologian.”*
- Jim Moretz, Pastor, Mt Moriah Wesleyan Church (Candler, NC), *“The Descriptive Connection between Scripture and Contemporary Life.”*

Practical Theology

Theme: “Scripture and the Public Life: Reading/Performing the Text as Engagement”

- Moderator: John Grant, Pastor, Shelton Church
- Panelists (all from Boston University):
 - Bryan Stone
 - Xochitl Alvizo
 - Nell Becker Sweeden
 - Josh Sweeden

Ecumenical Studies

- Moderator: Keelan Downton, World Council of Churches
- H. Mathias Zahniser, Greenville College, *“Can the Qur’an Serve as Deuterocanonical Scripture for Muslim Background Believers in the New Testament Jesus?”*
- Gordon Coulter, Azusa Pacific University, *“How to Be Ecumenical and Not Dilute or Give Up Your Wesleyan Theological Heritage: University and Church Relations.”*
- Keelan Downton, World Council of Churches, *“Ancient Authors, Younger Churches: A Response to the WCC Study on Sources of Authority.”*

- Brian Cooper, Azusa Pacific University, *“Orthosocietas: A Wesleyan Ecclesiology for the 21st Century Church.”*

Systematic Theology

- Moderator:
- Michael Lodahl, Point Loma Nazarene University, *“Incarnational Revelation: Why Christians, Despite the Qur’an, Are Not Really ‘People of the Book.’”*
- Nell Becker Sweeden (Boston University) and Brent D. Peterson (Northwest Nazarene University), *“Word and Table: Encountering the Holy to be Renewed as the Body of Christ.”*
- Thomas Oord, Northwest Nazarene University, *“Love as Central for Biblically-Oriented Systematic Theology: An Alternative to Hays, Hauwerwas, Collins, Dunning, and Wynkoop.”*

9:20-10:20 Poster Presentations and Women Students’ Reception

10:30-11:50 Parallel Session #5

Scripture (A)

Theme: “Canonical Approaches to Scripture”

- Moderator: Robert W. Smith, Point Loma Nazarene University
- David F. Watson, United Theological Seminary, *“Canonical Theism and Scripture: Reflections on a Scholarly Project Ten Years After Its Birth.”*
- Frank Anthony Spina, Seattle Pacific University, *“Canon, Community, Concubine: Biblical Authority or Ecclesial Authority?”*
- Daniel B. Spross, Trevecca Nazarene University, *“Contemporary Wesleyan Hermeneutics: Endless Dialectic or Canonical Consensus?”*

Scripture (B)

Theme: “Interpreting the New Testament II”

- Moderator: Carol Rotz, Northwest Nazarene University
- Bradley Thomas Johnson, Asbury Theological Seminary, *“The Baptism of John: A Contextual Examination of Intertestamental Baptismal Practices and Beliefs.”*
- Sarah K. Whittle, Nazarene Theological College, *“Bodies Given for the Body: Covenant, Community, and Consecration in Romans 12:1.”*

- Kenneth Milton Loyer, Southern Methodist University, “*Fruitfulness, Love, and Friendship in John 15: Toward a Synthetic Interpretation.*”

Historical Studies

- Moderator: Sun Ae Lee-Koo, The Catholic University
- Kevin Matthew Watson, Southern Methodist University, “*Forerunners of the Early Methodist Band Meeting.*”
- Patrick A. Eby, Drew University, “*Images of Perfection in Charles Wesley’s Short Hymns on Select Passages of the Holy Scriptures (1762).*”
- Stanley J. Rodes, Nazarene Theological College (Manchester, UK): “*To the Law and to the Testimony: John Wesley and the Enduring Word of the Lord.*”
- Mark K. Olson, Nazarene Theological Seminary, “*How Faith Tradition Shapes Our Reading of Scripture. A Case Study: The Stillness Controversy of the 1740’s.*”

Systematic Theology

- Gerald Chien Liu, Vanderbilt University, “*The Eschatological Witness of the Wesleyan Eucharistic Hymns: Developing What Sounds Like a Wesleyan Soteriology of Theology of Scripture.*”
- Nathan John Willowby, Marquette University, “*The Role of Scripture in Barth’s Relation Between Theology and Ethics.*”
- John L. Drury, Princeton Theological Seminary, “*Scripture as Testimony: A Critical Appropriation of the Concept of Testimony in the Wesleyan/Holiness Tradition for the Doctrine of Scripture.*”
- Michael W. McGowan, Claremont Graduate University, “*Evangelicals and Scripture: Contemporary Movements in the Doctrine of Revelation.*”

Ethnic Studies

Planning Session for the Future of the Ethnic Studies Section. All interested are encouraged to attend.

Moral Theology

Theme: “Virtue and the Natural Law”

- Moderator: Joseph Bankard, Northwest Nazarene University
- Craig Boyd, Azusa Pacific University, *A Shared Morality* (Baker, 2007).
- Kevin Lowery, Olivet Nazarene University, *Sabvaging Wesley’s Agenda* (Wipf & Stock, 2008).

Practical Theology

- Moderator: Doug Hardy, Nazarene Theological Seminary

- Chris Adams, Azusa Pacific University, *“Word and Table: Encountering the Holy to be Renewed as the Body of Christ.”*
- Jeffery A. Conklin-Miller, The Divinity School at Duke University, *“The People Who Became a People: The Ecclesiological Significance of the General Rules.”*
- Jay Akkerman, Northwest Nazarene University, *“Fractal Ministry.”*

12:00-12:50 Closing Worship

1:00-2:30 Lunch and Meeting of Program Chairs

LOCATION:

Azusa Pacific University
901 E. Alostia Ave.
Azusa, CA 91702-7000

Map: <http://www.apu.edu/maps/online/>

The evening banquets will be in the Upper Turner Campus Center on APU's East Campus. All other sessions will be in APU's West Campus.

ON-SITE REGISTRATION will be held at the meeting location (see above for directions).

ACCOMMODATIONS: We have made arrangements with these hotels. Mention your attendance at this meeting in order to receive the special rate for the conference:

Doubletree Hotel Monrovia - Pasadena Area

924 West Huntington Drive, Monrovia, California, United States 91016

Tel: 1-626-357-1900

http://doubletree1.hilton.com/en_US/dt/hotel/LAXMVDT-Doubletree-Hotel-Monrovia-Pasadena-Area-California/index.do

Shilo Inn Hilltop Suites Hotel

3101 Temple Avenue

Pomona. CA 91768

Ph: 909-598-7666 ext. 274

<http://www.shiloinns.com>

Participants should reserve rooms by February 6 in order to be assured of accommodations at these rates.

TRANSPORTATION AND PARKING:

1. Parking is free at the hotels
2. A shuttle between hotels and the conference site will be available. Please indicate on the registration form if you anticipate needing this shuttle.
3. Transportation to/from airport:
 - Shilo Inn has a complimentary shuttle to and from Ontario Airport
 -

Special needs? Handcapped

Presenters: Indicate technology needs

Address for vendors to ship

REGISTRATION FORM:

- Save money by registering by February 17
- You can register online at this site: <https://commerce.cashnet.com/WTS>
- If you do not wish to pay online, mail this form with a check or money order to :

Samuel M. Powell
WTS 2009 Annual Meeting Registration
Point Loma Nazarene University
3900 Lomaland Drive,
San Diego, California 92106

Name _____

(Name tag will be printed this way, without indicating academic degrees)

Institution _____

Mailing Address

City _____ State/Province _____

Zip/Postal Code _____ Country _____

E-mail _____

Telephone (Office) _____ (Home) _____

Will you need transportation from hotel to the conference site?

Yes No

REGISTRATION FEE:

- Thursday March 4, 2010. Meeting of the Wesleyan Philosophical Society and the Society for the Study of Wesleyan Theology and Psychology. *The registration fee includes membership in the society of your choice.*

Students\$35.00

Full members\$55.00

Please indicate your affiliation:

WPS

SSWTP

I decline membership in either WPS or SSWTP

- Friday March 5 and Saturday March 6, 2010. Meeting of the Wesleyan Theological Society.

For registrations postmarked by February 17:

Student members\$30.00

Full members\$80.00

Non-members.....\$110.00

For registrations postmarked after February 17:

Student members.....\$40.00

Full members.....\$100.00

Non-members.....\$130.00

If you are paying the non-member rate, please indicate whether you wish to have a complimentary one-year membership in the Wesleyan Theological Society

yes no.

PURCHASE BROWN BAG LUNCHES: Purchase by

March 1 to guarantee availability.

Thursday\$8.75

Turkey sandwich Egg salad sandwich Chicken Caesar salad wrap

Friday\$8.75

Turkey sandwich Egg salad sandwich Italian pesto chicken wrap

Saturday\$8.75

Turkey sandwich Egg salad sandwich Italian pesto chicken wrap

PURCHASE A BANQUET TICKET (Registration for the meeting is not required for attendance at the banquets.)

Tickets must be purchased by March 1, 2010, in order to guarantee a seat. BANQUET TICKETS MUST BE PRE-ORDERED; THEY CANNOT BE PURCHASED AT THE CONFERENCE.

Thursday (Buffet).....\$25.00

Friday (Buffet)\$25.00

TOTAL FEES: \$ _____